

Chapter 6 Construction and testing of a mockup to investigate the mechanical behavior of a wax-resin lined painting

Outline of the chapter

- Introduction
 - Definition of the elastic moduli and characterization of the materials
- Materials and methods
 - The wax-resin lining of the mockup painting
 - The tensile tests
 - The new flexural testing tower and the flexural tests
 - The tensile and flexural moduli
- Results and discussion
 - Morphological data on the textiles
 - Tensile response of the materials under biaxial and uniaxial testing
 - The lining canvas
 - The effect of wax-resin on the lining canvas
 - The naturally aged painting
 - The mechanical behavior of the lined mockup and the calculation of the elastic moduli
 - Calculation of the loaded section area of the mockup
- Elaborations about the possible elastic moduli of The Night Watch
- Conclusions and future work

Introduction

Paintings on canvas are complex, multi-layered structures composed of canvas, size, ground and paint layers, varnishes and the materials from past conservation treatments, such as consolidation and lining adhesives, and additional lining supports. Research into the mechanics of canvas paintings is limited by such complexity, but perhaps even more so by the fact that most mechanical tests require meaningful samples of suitable dimensions to be taken from the painting. This is easy to understand, since in order to know how much force is needed to stretch, bend, or break a material, it is necessary to test a physical object. The values of the Elastic Modulus and of the Ultimate Strength are the cornerstones of materials engineering, and the procedures to obtain them require cutting a sample with a defined shape, and submitting it to destructive testing¹. Attempts have been made in engineering and conservation science to reduce sample dimensions to the nano scale [Tiennot et al., 2020], and the micro scale [Maraghechi et al., 2023], which are very promising but need to be correlated with the macroscopic, or real size, scale of the artifact. Understanding the mechanical properties of a painting is crucial for conservators in evaluating the effects of stretcher tension on their structural integrity. As we saw in chapter 5, the conservation and conservation science literature offer very little data on the tensile response of canvas paintings, and practically nothing is available for the evaluation or quantification of its flexibility through its flexural elastic modulus.

¹ Ennio Sorta, in "Problemi di Conservazione" [Sorta, 73], proposed to use a Dynamic modulus tester, DMT PPM-5R produced by Lawson Hemphill (Swansea, MA) to measure of E Modulus of paintings. The non-destructive method, based on the use of an elastic wave, has never been used. The original paper can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14834185>

This chapter presents the design, construction, and use of a physical mockup of a wax-resin-lined painting that draws inspiration from the structure of Rembrandt's 1642 wax-resin lined oil painting known as *The Night Watch*². The mockup consists of a large fragment of a 17th-century Italian canvas painting, that was lined following the procedures used for the 1975 lining of *The Night Watch*. The purpose is to obtain otherwise inaccessible information on the mechanical/structural behavior of wax-resin lined paintings, but also to openly discuss the challenges and benefits of implementing this type of information in the conservation science and practice. Mechanical tests were performed on the mock-up using the custom-built equipment described in chapter 4, to measure its tensile and flexural response.

The mockup is used to describe the mechanical behavior of the constituent layers and of the assembled structure. It was built as a research object destined to provide material for destructive mechanical testing using the equipment described in chapter 4. The debate about the use of mockups and models in science has always been very lively, also on a general epistemological level [Cassini and Redmond, 2022]. The topic is often discussed in conservation science, and the value and limitations of the use of models have been analyzed, as in [Stoveland et al. 2021; dePolo et al. 2021]. Physical simulations are sometimes considered unreliable with respect to the materials used, their aging³, and the variability of the original structures. This leads to a kind of prejudice that favors digital simulations because they appear to be more anodyne and because they produce quantitative results that can be adjusted to real data by simply working on the numerical parameters of the model rather than with the complex and time-consuming production of a new physical model. However, if validation is relatively easy when dealing with new or reproducible artifacts, as in standard engineering, it becomes very difficult with heritage materials that cannot be sacrificed for destructive testing.

An interesting by-product of constructing a handmade artifact to simulate the painting's build-up is that it allows the behavior of the layered structure to be studied in detail. The mere checking of the model's adherence and differences from the original is an opportunity to test the assumptions on which the interpretation of the structures is based. This process is thus an advanced expression of all the investigation modes, both morphological and mechanical, developed in this thesis research. It also required the adaptation of the mechanical testing machine to carry out flexural tests according to ASTM D 790-07 (see fig. 61b and 62), what is, per se, a further improvement in material testing of canvas paintings materials because no precedent was found in the literature.

Definition of the elastic moduli and characterization of the materials

As discussed in chapter 2, stretched canvas paintings are composite objects made up of canvas, preparation layers, paint and varnish layers. The complexity can be further increased by the presence of a lining canvas and lining adhesive. Test results describing the tensile response of a painting are crucial in the evaluation of the effects of stretcher tension on the structural integrity of paintings, and could therefore be helpful also for conservators.

² The full name of the painting is: "Officers and other civic guardsmen of District II in Amsterdam, under the command of Captain Frans Banninck Cocq and Lieutenant Willem van Ruytenburch". The large oil painting (before the start of the structural treatment it measured: 379.5 x 453.5 cm) is on loan to the Rijksmuseum from the City of Amsterdam since 1808, with the inv. no SK-C-5.

³ As seen in the Introduction, a lively public debate about the use of aging protocols of materials used in [Carr et al., 2003], to mimic the mechanical behavior of a "typical 19th c. English painting", can be found in *Studies in Conservation*, vol 49 (2004), in the Letters to the Editors at p. 70-72.

As discussed in chapter 5, the value of the cross-section area of the sample is a key factor to calculate the tensile modulus, that allows comparing the response of different materials. Young's modulus is also necessary to use software allowing engineering simulations and modeling, the finite element models (FEM), that can be useful to predict and investigate a painting's structural behavior. A common approach to determining the tensile modulus of a composite material with different stiffness layers is to test them individually and calculate the weighted average of their moduli based on their thickness. The definition of Young's modulus is based on the assumption that the materials have a homogeneous structure, but canvas paintings are complex composite structures, and contain voids at the macro as well as the micro scale. The methods used for reducing the cross section of a painting to a homogeneous material as required in the definition of the Young's modulus are an open research question. When dealing with an untreated textile, precedents in the literature are available involving the calculation of the cross-section of the fibers reacting to the tensile load. The procedure is based on subtracting the empty spaces between the fibers and between the yarns, and the area is often approximated to about 25% of the textile's cross-section. Equation [7] was developed to quantify the fiber equivalent cross-section in each textile with increased accuracy. When a stiff material is superimposed and well bonded to another of lesser stiffness, the tensile modulus is often calculated as if from the stiffest material alone. Determining the flexural (bending) modulus of a layered material depends on the stiffness and thickness of each layer as well as their contribution to the flexural stiffness, with materials farther from the neutral axis contributing more to the flexural rigidity.

The morphology of the textiles involved in the construction of the mockup was analyzed using the protocol described in chapter 3, and tensile tests were performed on each layer of the mockup. Data on the lining canvas, specimen n. 23, was already available, as it was morphologically described in chapter 3 and mechanically characterized in chapter 5. To gain a more detailed understanding of the material behavior, aside with the biaxial tests, additional uniaxial tests were performed on specimen 23 and on the 17th century painting fragment. The specimen available of the 1975 lining canvas, from the lower right corner of The Night Watch, was not large enough to perform both biaxial and uniaxial tensile tests, so biaxial testing was preferred⁴. The mechanical characterization of the 1975 lining canvas also provided an insight about the quantification of the naturally aged wax-resin it contains and its influence on the tensile response.

Materials and methods

The Rijksmuseum's Paintings Conservation Department still holds pieces of lining canvas that have a comparable weave and thread density to the canvas used to line The Night Watch. Wax-resin lining is no longer used in the Rijksmuseum since the end of the 1980s and the canvas is likely a few decades old. This canvas was provided (specimen n. 23) and used for the mock-up. A piece of the 1975 lining canvas from the lower right corner of the tacking margin of The Night Watch was also investigated for comparison (fig. 58). The two textiles were supplied by Claessens in Belgium, the company confirms having supplied the canvas for The Night Watch lining, and the item is still available for sale with the code 026⁵. As we will see, the slight differences found between the two lining textiles (the one used in 1975 and that of the mockup, n. 23) are consistent with the variability of woven structures from natural fibers.

⁴ Not all the specimen was used, and material is still available to repeat the tests, or to perform uniaxial tests.

⁵ The web link to the product they are selling today is: <https://www.claessenscanvas.com/en/products/canvas/detail/026>

Fig. 58 Detail of the basket weave canvas used in the 1975 lining of The Night Watch after removing most of the wax-resin adhesive. Top left, the hole of a steel nail used in the tacking margin.

The naturally aged painting used for the mockup was a 19th century extension of a 17th century painting. The cross section (fig. 59) shows that an earlier painting had been used for the extension and is now hidden under a thick overpaint. Such 19th century oil-based paint layer (about 350 μm thick in the cross section) contains lamp black, earth colors, lead white, and prussian blue in the finishing layers. The underlying original oil painting also contains lead white, and shows a discolored varnish at the interface with the overpaint. The original paint layers contain smalt blue, a pigment which was commonly used in the 16th and 17th centuries, and present an oil-based ground on the pure linen canvas. Original ground and paint layers are relatively thin (about 60 μm), and the presence of the overpaint increases the overall thickness with additional naturally aged paint materials. The specimen bears a thick layer of paste glue, as it had been lined in the 19th century. Most of the paste glue was removed using an agarose gel to soften it, but not all could be extracted and some still impregnates the painting. The presence of 19th c. paste glue residues is a common point with The Night Watch, that had also been paste lined before the 1852 wax-resin lining. At the end of the process, the average thickness of our specimen was 0.727 mm and its weight 693 g/m².

Fig. 59 Cross section of the naturally aged painting used to simulate The Night Watch in the mockup. 10x magnification, a) visible light, b) ultraviolet light (credit: Giorgia Agresti)

The wax-resin lining of the mockup painting

The lining for the mockup was done by Justine Sionneau⁶, with the participation of the author, following the wax-resin method used in 1975 to line *The Night Watch*, as described in [Kuiper and Hesterman, 1976]. The mixture of 5 parts of beeswax and 2 parts of colophony was melted and applied by brush on the lining canvas, then ironed to make it penetrate the painting and create an evenly distributed layer, connecting the two canvases upon cooling. The completed mockup is 1.83 mm thick and weighs 1701 g/m², meaning that the lining canvas and adhesive have added about 1 mm in thickness and almost exactly 1 kg/m² of weight (to a painting weighing about 0,7 kg/m²). Such weight is surprisingly close to that of *The Night Watch*, estimated in 1705 g/m² (as we will see in chapter 7). The variability in the thickness of the impasto, and the different material properties of the painting influence the local behavior in ways that a mock-up could not possibly replicate. Nevertheless, as the lining canvas and the lining method strongly characterize the mechanics of a lined painting, this mockup is considered to be an acceptable approximation for a 17th c. wax-resin lined painting aiming to emulate the structure of *The Night Watch*.

Tensile tests on the individual layers were performed to evaluate and quantify their influence on the tensile response of the complete mockup. As the wax-resin adhesive is permeating all layers, in order to prepare the samples, it was necessary to decide how much of it should be applied to each layer for the individual tests. The decision was made to try and replicate the quantity of adhesive found in the 1975 lining canvas from the tacking margin⁷ of *The Night Watch*, in order to obtain data that may also describe the materials of the painting the mockup is inspired to. Subtracting the weight of the clean canvas provided from that of the 1975 sample would have been an easy solution to obtain the weight of the adhesive, but based on the assumption that the clean canvas sample is the same as that used in 1975, which cannot be stated with absolute certainty. Therefore, an indirect approach was taken aiming at the reproduction of the quantities present in the different layers.

Part of the 1975 specimen was treated so as to extract the adhesive mixture with heat, ironing the samples between layers of absorbent paper until no visible residues were left on the paper. The difference in weight, about 120 g/m², is the quantification of the material exceeding the closest interaction with the fibers. To better describe the quantity of wax-resin adhesive in the canvas, a parallel with the possible quantities of water in wood is very useful. Saturated wood dries in two distinct phases: during the first, water defined as “free water” empties the hollow lumen of the cells and channels; during the second, the water within the fibers, defined as “bound water”, evaporates, leaving the wood completely anhydrous. In our parallel, the untreated lining canvas is in the anhydrous state, and the 1975 specimen from the tacking margin is in the saturated condition. The wax-resin that remained after the heat extraction process is considered like the “bound water”, dependent on the characteristics of the specific textile, while the extracted quantity is the “free water”, and the quantity of adhesive that can be measured. In our case, the “bound adhesive” was replicated on the clean lining canvas and on the mockup painting by impregnating them and then removing the excess using the same procedure, until reaching the “bound” configuration. This process allowed quantifying the bound adhesive, that is, approx. 90 g/m². The “free water” configuration was replicated by adding the wax-resin mixture to the “bound” configuration until the

⁶ French conservator from the Atelier Buti, Le Poiré sur Vie, 85170 France. She has established wax-resin lining practicing experience.

⁷ This does not represent the actual quantity of adhesive present in the lining because the sample has never been in contact with the painting (as it was taken from the tacking margin), and the wax-resin was thinned down in Feb. 2022, during the structural treatment.

quantity of approx. 120 g/m² found in the 1975 specimen was reached, by gradually repeating the procedures used for lining. This configuration was therefore defined as “emulated” (table 26).

material weight (g/sqm)	clean	bound	emulated
1975 lining canvas from The Night Watch		449	565
mockup lining canvas	380	466	589
sample painting	693	801	

Table 26. Weight of the textiles with the different quantities of the wax resin mixture.

The tensile tests

As described in chapter 5, all specimens were laser cut to the sample shape required with the tensile tester. Biaxial samples were cut into a cruciform shape providing a sharp 10x10 mm test area, which extends into 5x10 mm arms on each side to be used for clamping. A small V-shaped indentation is cut in the clamping areas corresponding to the weft in order to keep the information in the otherwise symmetrical sample (as seen in fig. 9, chapter 3). The uniaxial samples are simple 20x10 mm strips, with the same V-shaped indentation if aligned with the weft, or with a semicircular one if prepared along the warp.

As seen in chapter 4, the tensile tester is equipped with two pairs of actuators, motors that move a load cell and a sample clamp on each axis (Fig. 61 a). Their simultaneous motion ensures that the center of the cruciform sample always remains in the same position throughout the test, while the four ends are moving. Homogeneous distribution of the tension in the sample at the beginning of each test is assured with the pretensioning procedure (fig. 38). This is based on micrometric displacements of the four actuators, in laps, until the four load cells read the same target value. The use of four load cells also allows anomalies to be read during the tensile test, and the mean value of the pair of opposing load cells provides the value for each axis. Uniaxial tests performed with the device are instead equal to the standard tensile procedures, with the only difference that the overall motion and speed are divided between the two opposing motors. Measuring the tensile response of the two axes simultaneously makes testing conditions closer to those of a painting on stretcher. This is because biaxial testing also measures the interaction of the yarns in the two directions, an information that is lost in uniaxial tests (as discussed in chapters 2, 4 and 5). Tests were performed at the speed of 2 mm/min, or 1 mm/min for each actuator.

The new flexural testing tower and the flexural tests

The flexural experimental setup is based on the use of only one of the four actuators, applying orthogonal force at the center of the sample while it is resting on a support allowing it to bend from two fixed points in a “three-point bending” procedure. A flexural testing tower was designed and built, that holds the sample in front of the two supports, while standing free of constraints on the sample rest, and a steel plate moves perpendicular to its center at the speed of 0.5 mm/min, reaching it with a rounded contact blade parallel to its surface (fig. 60b and fig. 61). In order to meet the testing standard requirements for the ratios between length, width and thickness of the material (ASTM D 790 – 07), slightly bigger samples were needed, measuring 26x55 mm⁸. The ASTM standard is

⁸ According to ASTM D 790 – 07, for materials at least 1.6 mm thick, a minimum ratio of 16 between the length (including the overhangs after the supports) and the thickness of the sample is required, while the width needs to be at least twice the thickness. Samples for

designed for use with Universal Testing Machines, in which the load is applied vertically. To be used with the biaxial tensile tester, the flexural testing tower keeps the sample vertical against the supports as the actuators move horizontally. The influence of gravity appears nevertheless neglectable, what allows considering the procedure equivalent to the ASTM standard for this particular application.

Fig. 60 The biaxial tester clamps (a); the flexural tower holding the sample vertical against one of the actuators (b).

Fig. 61 CAD design of the flexural tower holding the sample vertical in front of the two supports.

The tensile and flexural moduli

The definition and use of the tensile modulus (E) was already introduced in chapters 4 and 5, as the ratio between stress and strain ($E = \text{stress} / \text{strain}$) where $\text{stress} = \text{force} / \text{area}$ (the tensile force acting on the area of the cross section of the sample) and $\text{strain} = \text{elongation} / \text{length}$ (the difference in length due to the test, divided by the initial length). So, if stress is a description of the force acting on the sample, strain provides an indication of the response of the sample to that force and this makes E a key factor in materials engineering. A high value of E describes a material with a high resistance to deformation, and a low value of strain indicates that a given force has little effect on the material being tested. The standard equation for E modulus [1] is recalled here, where F is the force, w is the sample width, h is its thickness, L_0 the initial length and L_f the elongated length of the sample.

the flexural tests were 55 mm long, 1.83 mm thick and 26 mm wide; the distance between the supports on the flexural tower (fixed in the center of the device) is 47.4 mm.

$$E = \frac{\frac{F}{wh}}{\frac{(Lf-L_0)}{L_0}} \quad [1]$$

The flexural modulus (E_f) is a special case for E , describing the resistance the material offers to bending. The resistance to bending depends on the distance between the two supports (correlated to length of the sample) and the point of application of the force at the center, but also on the thickness of the sample and its width. The standard equation [8] must therefore include all variables, and L is the distance between the supports, F is the force, w is the width of the sample, h is its thickness, d is the deflection.

$$E_{flex} = \frac{L^3 F}{4wh^3 d} \quad [8]$$

The two Elastic moduli were calculated according to equations [1 and 8] and, considering the complexity of the layered structure, the decision was made to keep it in the form of “object related” E modulus described in chapter 5. The structural description of an unlined painting has been treated in previous literature, and the subject analyzed in chapter 5 with several examples, but that of a lined painting is a subject needing further investigation, as no precedent was found in the literature.

Results and discussion

Morphological data on the textiles

The morphological analysis of the two lining textiles (the one used in 1975 and that of the mockup, n. 23) is a useful example to describe the insights and possibilities offered by the new protocols introduced in chapter 3. The first level of observation, the thread count, shows that the values for the two textiles are very similar: 19 warps and 15 wefts for the 1975 lining canvas (lower right corner of *The Night Watch*) versus 20 warps and 16 wefts for the one used for the mockup (n. 23). The thread count of a textile (see chapter 3) is the subject of many textile engineering studies, and automated methods have been proposed since the second half of the 20th c. [Hosseini and Toriumi, 1995]. Manual counting the yarns is a time-consuming operation that easily incurs in experimental error, but it should also be considered that the thread count is not constant within the same textile. Therefore, in order to obtain values representing the textile, and not only a relatively small area of observation, a valid alternative is counting on large areas (possibly with an automated method) [van der Maaten and Erdmann, 2015] and obtain its average value. Working on small samples, as in all the specimens in this research, the expected variability in the readings on the same textile is about 5-10% (as it can be seen in table 3 and fig. 17). The difference between the two textiles is therefore compatible with the possibility that they are from the same production. Moreover, as the 1975 textile was well stretched during the lining process, yarn spacing may result slightly increased. The data sheet from Claessens website shows that the textile sold today has the slightly different thread-count of 20.5 warps and 14.5 wefts, what still falls within the expected variability. A general consideration is that the warp count is the backbone of a textile organized on the loom at the beginning of the weaving process, while the number of weft yarns cast during the production can be changed by reducing the frequency of the spool in the shed. As we have seen in chapter 3, a slight reduction of the weft count ensures a cheaper production while not introducing substantial changes in the quality and performance of the canvas.

The observation protocols provided a quantitative insight on their structures (see table 27), showing very similar data for the two textiles. The crimp value is almost identical in the warp yarns (7.16 and 7.20 %) and very similar in the weft yarns (1.58 and 1.42 %); in the weft yarns, also yarn width (0.46 and 0.42 mm), thickness (0.31 and 0.29 mm) and twist count (262 and 269 TPM) are highly compatible. The only relevant difference is found in the width of the warp yarns, which is thinner in the 1975 canvas (0.69 and 0.56 mm). As the specimen is taken from the perimeter, the hypothesis that the difference could be due to mechanical stresses incurred with pliers to stretch the painting during or after the lining, was tested and not confirmed. The reason is that if those warp yarns had become thinner because of a mechanical stress after weaving they should not display a higher twist count (181 and 213 TPM). Twist is a characteristic of the yarn preceding the weaving of the textile, and a thinner yarn normally has higher twist (table 5, chapter 3). The thinner and more twisted warp yarns measured in the 1975 samples are not due to conservation history but represent the textile. Moreover, a mechanical stress would have changed their local crimp, and the new form would have been stabilized by the massive presence of wax-resin. Therefore, as the crimp is not different, those warp yarns were actually slightly thinner during the textile production.

The method used to obtain yarn width and twist values includes a form of statistical treatment of the data, as the weighted means are calculated on the basis of the relative dimensional classes of the yarns. But still, as the measures could only be taken in areas measuring 10x10 mm, the limited quantity of data does not allow applying the statistical distribution of the entire textile. The case is therefore similar to the comparison of the thread count in the textiles. The morphological descriptions of the two textiles appear to be close enough to justify the statement that the differences are consistent with the variability of woven structures from natural fibers and fall within the natural variability of the same production.

Morphological data on the canvases used to build the mockup						
Yarns described		Thread count/cm	Crimp (%)	Twist (TPM)	Thickness (mm)	Width (mm)
Mockup lining canvas	Warp	20	7,16	181	0,27	0,69
	Weft	16	1,58	262	0,31	0,46
1975 lining canvas	Warp	19	7,20	213	0,33	0,56
	Weft	15	1,42	269	0,29	0,42
Naturally aged painting	Warp	10	3,09	151	0,35	0,77
	Weft	9	2,93	252	0,39	0,63

Table 27. Numerical data on the yarns of the three canvases.

Tensile response of the materials under biaxial and uniaxial testing

Tensile tests on the materials allow the structure and mechanical behavior of the mockup to be described. All tests were carried out at 20°C (+/- 0.5)⁹, and 50% (+/- 5) relative humidity, at the same speed of 2 mm/min on at least 3 samples for each specimen¹⁰. Sample have the same dimensions (10 mm wide) and gauge length (10,6 mm). Tensile data in table 28 are taken for the same 1,89% strain, corresponding to the location B of the data in chapter 5 (fig. 50 and table 10). The choice of a relatively low value of elongation is due to the fact that the overall goal here is to study the tensile response of

⁹ Special care was given to the control of temperature, seen the presence of the wax.

¹⁰ With the exception of the "1975 bound wax", for which only one sample was available.

the mockup in a range of forces not too far from those a painting experiences during treatment, handling and environmental changes. When compared to the secant modulus of the other textiles (table 10, chapter 5) all values appear to be within the expected range.

In the existing literature, as seen in the section "*The E modulus values in the conservation science literature*" of chapter 5, the values also appear to be within the same range. The comparison must nevertheless take into account that the *E*-modulus value in the literature is the general *E*-modulus, referring to strains closer to C or D rather than to the B (1,89 %) strain chosen here (fig. 62, fig. 50), and are likely to take higher values. Still, in biaxial testing the tensile modulus is generally higher (table 28) and this is probably compensating for such difference because most of the literature values refer to uniaxial loading. In any case, if the modulus of textiles has very few literature references to compare with, that of painting materials is even more rare, and the value of *E* for naturally aged paintings is not currently available for comparison. The data in table 28 is a clear example of the different test results obtained with uniaxial and biaxial loading, and the role of crimp in developing tensile response. Uniaxial tensile tests show 89 times lower response in the warp (because of the high crimp and low twist), and the warp/weft ratio is only 12 in the biaxial tests due to the stiffness transfer between the yarns during simultaneous loading. The phenomenon of crimp transfer, or "crimp interchange" [Behera and Hari, 2010] is clearly seen in fig. 63, where the biaxial testing mitigates the difference in tensile response between warp and weft. The weft yarns complete the decrimping phase well before the warp yarns, reducing the latter's decrimping by creating a rigid constraint in the woven structure. The warp yarns begin to respond to tension earlier, and experience a "stiffness transfer" from the weft yarns, which in turn experience a reduction in tensile response.

test values at B (1,89% strain)	test	direction	force (N)	E (MPa)	E ratio
mockup lining canvas	uniaxial	warp	0,3	2,4	88,67
		weft	29,3	215,4	
mockup lining canvas, bound wax-resin	uniaxial	warp	0,6	4,5	36,80
		weft	23,6	166,4	
mockup lining canvas, emulated wax-resin	uniaxial	warp	2,5	16,1	4,43
		weft	10,9	71,4	
mockup lining canvas	biaxial	warp	2,5	18,0	11,77
		weft	28,8	212,3	
mockup lining canvas, bound wax-resin	biaxial	warp	2,4	17,2	7,82
		weft	19,1	134,9	
mockup lining canvas, emulated wax-resin	biaxial	warp	4,2	27,7	3,24
		weft	13,7	89,8	
1975 lining canvas, bound wax-resin	biaxial	warp	17,7	125,4	2,29
		weft	40,6	286,6	
1975 lining canvas, emulated wax-resin	biaxial	warp	16,1	101,7	2,41
		weft	38,9	245,3	
painting	uniaxial	warp	26,9	195,2	1,22
		weft	32,9	238,8	
painting	biaxial	warp	16,9	122,9	1,98
		weft	33,6	243,6	
painting, bound wax-resin	biaxial	warp	23,6	166,7	1,54
		weft	36,4	257,5	
complete mockup	biaxial	warp	35,5	102,8	0,98
		weft	34,8	100,6	

Table 28. The tensile response and secant tensile modulus at the same 1,89% strain (location B).

The lining canvas

Looking into the behavior of the lining canvas, it is of no surprise that it exhibits very different values in the warp and weft directions. In fig. 62, the plots show the evolution of the tensile response during the elongation of the samples. We know that crimp in the warp is much higher than in the weft (7.16 % vs. 1.58 %, table 27), and in fig. 63 we see the full plot of the uniaxial response in the warp direction. This shows a “pure decrimping behavior” [Kovar, 2011] (fig. 15, chapter 3) up to the elongation of 0.2 mm, during which almost no response from the textile is measured. A straight-line progression is seen up to about 1.2 mm, with a change in the slope around 1.5 mm suggesting a stiffening due to permanent deformation, and a new straight segment up to about 2.6 mm, when the material starts failing. The total elongation of the weft yarns is much shorter, with a similar slight change in slope at about 0.15 mm instead of 1.5 mm. The decrimping in the weft is also very short, and the tension build up is much steeper also because of higher cohesion provided by the higher twist (262 TPM vs. 181 TPM, table 27). Such differences in the morphology of warp and weft are relatively common in textiles, as seen in chapters 3 and 5, but still, their rather exceptional value seems to be a special characteristic for this basket weave canvas.

Fig. 62 The tensile response of the lining canvas in uniaxial and biaxial tests.

Fig. 63 Complete uniaxial plot of the warp tensile response

The effect of wax-resin on the lining canvas

The ratios between warp and weft in table 28 show that the presence of the lining adhesive introduces a stiffness transfer also in the uniaxial tests. In the first three lines we see the dramatic reduction of the ratio in uniaxial testing increasing the quantity of adhesive. Looking in more detail, we see that the ratio is reduced because the modulus increases in the warp and decreases in the weft. This also implies that the increase of wax-resin reduces the tensile response of the textile, as the weft reaches a force of 10.9 N (3 times less than of the initial value of 29.3 N) and the warp stays on very low values (though increasing 8 times). The reduction of the tensile modulus is also seen in the biaxial tests (the following three lines in table 28). It should be noted that the E modulus is reduced in the “emulated” configuration also because the thickness of the sample is slightly increased by the addition of wax-resin, and so is that of the cross section.

The information available in the literature on this subject can be summarized in the following three contributions. In [Berger, 1972] we see that impregnation causes chemical degradation of the fibers and a reduction of the mechanical performance of the textile after artificial aging (what does not apply to the present study because the 1975 wax-resin has always been protected from UV and heat sources). In [Hedley, 1975 b] five textiles were tested in three conditions: samples uniaxially tested in warp, in weft and at 45°. Tests were repeated after impregnation, and the stiffness was found to be increased in the initial region (strain about 2%, as in our B secant modulus). Another relevant result of that research is that the difference of the tensile response between the three tensile conditions was reduced after impregnation, witnessing a more isotropic behavior of the textile. In [Tassinari, 1973a] we see that the impregnation produces an increase of the stiffness and the ultimate load of the four textiles tested, in both the warp and weft directions. The results in table 28 seem therefore to be proposing a relatively unexpected behavior, possibly due to the uncommonly high difference in crimp between the warp and weft direction of the textile.

The green area of table 28 shows the values obtained with the biaxial testing of the 1975 lining. The first difference with the mockup lining canvas is that the difference between the “emulated” and the “bound” wax-resin quantities is less pronounced (about 14% for the 1975 lining instead of 34% for the mockup lining). The second is in the ratio between warp and weft is 37 for the mockup lining canvas and only 8 for the 1975 lining canvas in the “bound” configuration. But perhaps the most relevant difference is that the tensile modulus is always higher in the 1975 lining canvas than in the mockup lining canvas, also when untreated. The ratio between warp and weft is always lower than the lowest found for the other textile, suggesting that the adhesive provides a more effective stiffness transfer. The slight increase in the tensile reaction of the textile in the “bound” configuration, obtained by reheating the 1975 wax-resin, suggests that this has stronger adhesive properties, that increase with thermal reactivation. The modulus is also higher, but the difference is enhanced by the increase thickness of the samples due to the untouched wax-resin layer.

Since, as we have seen, the morphology of the two textiles is very similar, and the wax resin mixtures are intended to be as similar as possible, the information is unexpected. As suggested by the considerations above, and because the crimp in the two textiles is extremely similar, the reason for such a large difference in the mechanical behavior must lie in the adhesive. The possibilities seem to be either aging or a difference in the composition. The component most subjected to ageing is the colophony resin, but reduction of the mechanical performance would be expected due to aging breakdown of the molecular chains, rather than the substantially higher values measured. No information was found in the literature on the aging of wax-resin adhesives, because research naturally focuses on the effect of their presence in the painting rather than on their aging. Compositional differences cannot be ruled out, even though the mockup faithfully reproduced the available documentation [Kuiper and Hesterman, 1976]. Of course, a different composition could influence the tensile response, and the topic therefore requires further investigation and chemical analysis of the adhesives.

The naturally aged painting

In table 27 we see that the 17th century canvas of the painting fragment has relatively low crimp, and the warp and weft yarns share similar values for most of the measured characteristics. It is therefore no surprise that the tensile response of the naturally aged painting shows less difference between warp and weft, in both uniaxial and biaxial tests, if compared with the two lining canvases. The preparation and paint layers seem to have relevant influence on its mechanical behavior, since the values of force and of the E modulus do not show significative variations due to the wax-resin impregnation. It seems interesting to note that the presence of the “bound” wax-resin acts in this case as a consolidant, slightly improving the mechanical performance in the warp direction.

The mechanical behavior of the lined mockup and the calculation of the elastic moduli

The plots in fig. 64 describe the tensile behavior of the mockup, which is almost identical in warp and weft up to a tension of 45 N/cm (in the area identified as strain C), where they start diverging slightly. The orthotropic tensile response of the lining canvas is mitigated by the presence of the lining adhesive and is stabilized by the superpositions in the layered structure, as the ratio becomes close to 1 (table 28).

If, as stated in chapter 5, a straight-line tensile plot for such a complex composite structure does not guarantee a reversible elastic response, as if it were a homogeneous elastic material, a reversible elastic behavior seems to be extremely likely for the initial part of the plot. The tension values typically used for canvas paintings is located at the very beginning of the straight-line behavior of the mockup, if we consider that the Maximum Useful Tension (about 2.5 N/cm, chapter 2, fig. 7). For the mockup, MUT corresponds to the very low strain value of 0.13%, approx. 3 times smaller¹¹ than the strain at the location A for the tests listed in chapter 5, table 10.

Analyzing table 27 more in detail, we see that the biaxial tensile response of the mockup (35.5 N and 34.8 N) is higher than that of the lining canvas alone (2.5 N and 28.8 N)¹². This may imply that the 17th c. painting contributes to the stabilization of the sandwich, since the wax resin impregnation is found to reduce the tensile response of the lining canvas. But the increased isotropy, tensile response and overall tensile modulus may also be due to the stratification and superposition of the materials.

In conclusion, as the warp and weft values are very similar, the mockup can be considered as isotropic in the plane, with the “object related” secant tensile modulus in B of 102,8 MPa in warp and 100,6 MPa in weft, and a mean value of 101.7 MPa.

Fig. 64 The biaxial tensile results: load-elongation curve of warp and weft shows a very similar behavior: curves follow a straight line until 45 N/cm.

The flexural, or bending, tests (fig. 66) allow the value of the flexural modulus of the mockup to be calculated in about 1600 MPa, using equation [8]. The only reference for the flexural modulus of a canvas painting was found in [Chiriboga, 2013], where much lower bending stiffness values were found, because the mockup of an unlined painting was tested, built with a thin and flexible canvas and thin preparation and paint layers.

¹¹ The strain of 0.13%, is the elongation of 0.014 mm of the 10.6 mm sample.

¹² As previously discussed, and analyzed in chapter 5, the values of stress (and therefore of the tensile modulus) are less straightforward, though in this case they would allow for very similar conclusions.

Fig. 65 The flexural tests plot showing a wide linear response area.

Calculation of the loaded section area of the mockup

In the flexural tests, the force was applied to the verso of the painting, on the lining canvas¹³. This is therefore subjected to compression, while the paint layers undergo tensile loading. The lining canvas alone would have very low resistance to compression, but the presence of the lining adhesive stabilizes the yarns and fibers, and a relatively high stiffness can be expected from the wax-resin mixture in the initial phases of compression loading. On the other side of the sandwich, the tensile response of the oil-based preparation and paint layers depends on the pigments they contain, and the tensile modulus can be relatively high in the presence of metal ions [Mecklenburg, 2007]. The flexural test plot in fig 66, after a very short initial stiffening until 0.1 mm deflection, shows a substantially straight-line behavior until about 0.7 mm, progressing rapidly towards a drastic reduction of the resistance to bending, to the point that around the value of 0.9 mm it stops increasing.

To calculate the flexural modulus we have used equation [8], obtaining the value of 1600 MPa. No precedent is found in the literature, with the exception of [Chiriboga, 2013] who was dealing with completely different materials and testing methods. But looking into the flexural modulus of other classes of materials this value appears to be in the expected range. The decision was made to keep the flexural modulus as “object related”, because reducing the theoretical thickness as done for the tensile modulus, the values become too high. This is due to the highly sensitivity of equation [8] to the thickness of the material, as it appears at the denominator with a power of 3 ($/h^3$): all possible criteria for the reduction of the thickness lead to unjustifiably high values. To give an example, solving equation [8] for the equivalent thickness of the lining canvas alone (obtained with equation [7]) we obtain the value of 991 GPa for the flexural modulus, what is clearly out of range, since it would be about 5 times than that of steel (E_f 200 GPa). Using an intermediate value equivalent to the thickness

¹³ This was done to replicate the Displacement Tests that we will see in chapter 7, and those described in [Iaccarino Idelson, 2004].

of the two canvases and that of the paint layers, we obtain the E_f of good quality oak wood (20 GPa), still far too high if compared to that of any lined canvas painting. The value of 1600 MPa for the flexural modulus of the mockup seems therefore to be sufficiently backed up and ready to be used for digital engineering simulations and modeling (FEM).

The above mentioned “object related” tensile modulus value of 101.7 MPa is instead not usable in FEM, as it does not refer to a homogeneous material. The most used approach to solve this problem in engineering and conservation science, is that of using the tensile modulus of the stiffest material in the layered structure, assuming that this will be the one facing the loads [Mecklenburg, 1991]. The lining canvas alone, using equation [7] as in table 10 (chapter 5), displays a value of 825 MPa in weft for the secant modulus in B¹⁴. The stiffest layer of the 17th c. painting is the paint layer, as the original canvas is highly degraded, and the tensile modulus in B calculated for its thickness is 1271,9 MPa in warp and of 883,2 MPa in weft.

We therefore see that elaborating on the loaded section area of the layers constituting the mockup leads to considerably higher values. The value of the secant modulus in B being that of the stiffest layer, the 17th c. paint layers take the lead. As the mockup shows an isotropic tensile response, we may either use the highest value found in the stratigraphy, 1271,9 MPa in warp, or (to stay on the safe side) the average of the two directions, 1077,6 MPa. This value is further supported by the fact that the “object related” tensile modulus of 101.7 MPa appears to be unexpectedly different from the flexural modulus of 1600 MPa. Such a wide difference is typical of materials like sandwich composites, with high modulus outer layers kept at a distance by a softer core material, where a high bending stiffness is obtained thanks to the overall thickness, and the case does not seem to apply to a lined canvas.

Elaborations about the possible elastic moduli of The Night Watch

The data obtained with the mockup can be used to extrapolate the mechanical characteristics of The Night Watch, thanks to the information gathered about the tensile response of the sample from the lower right corner. As we have seen, the 1975 lining textile and adhesive appear to have a higher tensile modulus (245 MPa in weft, table 28) than the lining canvas used for the mockup (89 MPa in weft, table 28). Though no information is available about the modulus of the paint layers, it seems likely that the overall tensile modulus is slightly higher for The Night Watch.

As a matter of fact, calculating the tensile modulus of the 1975 lining and adhesive using equation [7] for the fiber section loading area we do obtain higher modulus values. In the “bound wax-resin configuration” we have 428,9 MPa in warp and 1524,4 MPa in weft; in the “emulated” we have 389,7 MPa in warp and 1460,8 MPa in weft.

Considering the previous research, described in chapter 5, the tensile modulus of textiles often exceeds 1 GPa [Young, 1996 a and b; Chiriboga, 2013] (tables 17-19). A precedent study, directly concerning The Night Watch is in Dings [Dings, 2022] where the range of tensile modulus for the painting was considered to be between 300 and 7000 MPa, and the FE simulations obtained a match with the painting’s deformation pattern. It seems therefore reasonable to assume the tensile

¹⁴ In general, the modulus is calculated for strains higher than B (i.e. C or D), where it normally meets higher values, and the value is 1143,7 MPa in C and 1372,9 MPa in D.

modulus of The Night Watch, including the contribution of the paint layers, to be not less than 1.5 GPa. The isotropy of the tensile response of the mockup (0.98 ratio between warp and weft) is related to the lining adhesive (the lining textile has a ratio of 3.24 after impregnation), and to the stratification including the painting. The 1975 lining sample has even more isotropic tensile response (ratio 2.41), therefore the assumption of a ratio close to 1 between warp and weft for The Night Watch appears to be robust.

Regarding the flexural modulus of The Night Watch, extrapolations are based on less evidence. However, two simple statements seem to stand. The first is that the investigated structure of the lined mockup is similar to that of the painting, with the main exceptions of a lining textile and adhesive which have a higher tensile modulus. The second is that the thickness of the mockup is a relatively common one, and is likely to be similar to that of the simpler areas of the painting where high impasto is not present. The Night Watch does indeed have areas of high impasto, and areas where large amounts of lead white and other metal ions favor the formation of high modulus paint layers. Such assumptions allow us to state with some confidence that the flexural modulus of The Night Watch is higher than that of the mockup, as stated for the tensile modulus.

In conclusion, if the structural integrity of the mockup subjected to the value of tension of about 2.5 N/cm (or the MUT, see fig. 64) appears to be ensured beyond any reasonable doubt, the same is true for The Night Watch, for which higher elastic moduli values are expected.

Conclusions and future work

The tensile and flexural modulus values are key factors in the implementation and use of digital simulations to predict the behavior of a painting. We have seen that such values can only be obtained using destructive mechanical testing as it was done for all the samples in this research. Similar values can be obtained for historical artifacts using nanoindentation (for the paint layers) [Tiennot et al., 2020], or microtensile testing (for individual fibers or yarns) [Maraghechi et al., 2023], methods that provide information about a small detail of the artwork that needs to be scaled up to the real-life size. An alternative approach is to use a FEM of the painting to reverse validate the values of the elastic moduli. The FEM must include all the forces and boundary conditions involved, and must be able to mimic the mechanical response of the painting to variations in loading conditions. In this way, a non-destructive mechanical test that can be performed on the painting to quantify its mechanical response, and replicated in the FEM. If the elastic modulus values used are correct, within a properly organized FEM, this will represent the same mechanical response measured on the physical object.

This has been organized for The Night Watch, and in the next chapter we will see the non-destructive mechanical test and the values of the mechanical response of the painting.

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